

A STUDY ON ONLINE PURCHASE ADDICTION AMONG NURSING STUDENTS

V.RAJA

Research Scholar (P.hD),
Dept.of Psychology, Annamalai University,
Annamalai Nagar - 608 002
India

Dr. J. M. ASGARALI PATEL

Associate Professor,
Dept.of Psychology, Annamalai University
Annamalai Nagar – 608 002
India

Abstract

Online purchase Dependent illness has drawn a lot of attention as it grows more and more integrated into our daily lives. Compared to most other segments of society, nursing students are more susceptible to becoming dependent on online purchases. The goal of the current study was to ascertain the degree of Dependent to online shopping and the reason behind nursing students' internet usage. In this study, 125 students (18–22 years old) from Puducherry's nursing program were chosen at random. Two surveys were distributed: one was a generic survey, and the other was Young's Internet addiction test. Subjects with mild (score 20–49), moderate (score 50–79), and severe (score 80–100) online Dependent were divided into three categories based on their scores. The results revealed that 61.25 percent of nursing students had a light online purchase Dependent, 30.50 percent had a moderate Dependent, and 8.25 percent had a severe online purchase Dependent. It was shown that

ordering food or snacks is the most frequent reason for making online purchases (50.06%), followed by ordering dresses or clothing (30.43%). Research revealed that 69.21% of students used the internet for less than three hours to make purchases, (22.79%) spent three to six hours online, and (8.0%) used the internet for up to eight or ten hours to place their orders. The issue of online purchase Dependent is becoming more prevalent among nursing students, and there is a significant level of online usage among them for ordering, playing games, watching movies, and using apps like (Zomato , Swiggy, Domino's Pizza, Amazon, Flipkart, Myntra, Nykaa , Ajo, Snapdeal, Meesho,Tatacliq, Facebook, and WhatsApp).

KEYWORDS: Online Purchase, Internet Dependent, Addiction, Nursing student & Nursing Lifestyle.

1.Introduction

People's lifestyles have changed in recent years. Going to crowded markets takes a lot of time and makes people uncomfortable. Hence, e-shopping is beneficial since it saves a lot of time. The act of purchasing goods, services, etc. directly from a vendor online without the use of a middleman service is known as online shopping. Online retailers allow customers to browse while lounging in their homes or while seated in front of a computer. Online retailers typically operate around the clock, and a large number of customers have access to the internet at both home and at work. Thus, online shopping is quite convenient for them. The ability to shop online and avoid standing in line or searching store to store for a certain item is one of the most alluring aspects of internet shopping, especially around the holidays. Online retailers offer a wide range of products. Thus, the researcher is interested in finding

out what the consumers want. Thus, information about fifty respondents' preferences for internet purchasing was gathered.

India has seen significant changes in many areas of its citizens' lives as a result of the concepts of westernization, globalization, and liberalization, including education, the growth of the IT sector, and an increase in international trade, brain drain, and more. The nation has advanced in several fields and shown that it can compete on a worldwide scale. India has also experienced rapid development in terms of Internet consumption; according to 2017 Internet world usage statistics, China leads the globe with 731.4 million users, followed by India with 462.1 million users and the United States with 286.9 users. Many people could not imagine their lives without the online purchase, which has become an essential element of daily existence. The ease of use of smart phones and the low cost of Internet connectivity have led to a rise in both personal and business use of the online purchase. Numerous options are available on the online purchase Foods , Travel, TV/ home appliances ,Fashions , Mobiles , Smart Gadgets ,Beauty and wellness , entertainment, and meeting needs related to daily living (such as booking a restaurant, finding information, staying informed about social and political concerns, etc.).

According to its definition, the Internet purchase is "a global computer network consisting of interconnected networks using standardized communication protocols that provides a variety of information and communication facilities." This definition makes it very clear that the term "Internet" refers to the global system of interconnected Internet protocol, which is a way to connect computers all over the world with the aid of servers and routers. Users of these connected computers can send and receive documents, emails, films, and other files as well

as text and voice messages. In addition to exchanging images and videos, the internet allows us to access any type of information at our fingertips by simply entering keywords. This includes historical, scientific, and entertaining content.

Internet addiction refers to the tendency to become addicted to particular websites, such as social networking sites, pornographic sites, and online shopping sites. These types of websites offer particularly alluring features.

2. Literature Review

The Internet has grown in importance as a medium for education, entertainment, communication, and information sharing in the new generation and is becoming a need in daily life worldwide (Nalwa & Anand, 2003), with young people being the primary users. Addiction to the internet is a major concern for young people. Among the many features of the Internet that encourage addictive behavior are social networking and easy access.

As of 2012, there were about 1.2 billion people living in India, of whom 205 million were Internet users (including urban and rural). By June 2014, it is predicted to reach 243 million, making India the second most popular nation after China, which presently has the largest Internet user base of 300 million people (Internet and Mobile Association of India, 2013).

The authors Hirschman and Holbrook (1982) propose that consumers are motivated to engage in online purchasing by both utilitarian and hedonistic factors. Some online shoppers can be characterized as "problem solvers," while others might be called "fun, fantasy, arousal, sensory stimulation and enjoyment" seekers.

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Nowadays, the majority of kids, teens, and even young adults are addicted to making purchases online. They buy cosmetics, dresses, ornaments, and other items online, as well as use it for enjoyment, conversation, and other purposes, taking up most of their valuable time. Because internet shopping has become such a big part of people's daily lives in the present era, it is influencing society in more and more ways. Both internationally and in India, the usage of online shopping has grown dramatically. The growing number of students making purchases online can be attributed to the increased development of network instruction in colleges and institutions. Scholars worldwide are paying attention to a number of issues stemming from the misuse of the Internet that coexist with excessive usage.

Goals for the research

1. To find out the extent to which nursing students make purchases online.
2. To research nursing students' motivations for using the internet for purchases.

Materials and Methods

A total of 125 nursing students, aged between 18 and 22, enrolled in nursing programs in Puducherry were included in this investigation. The subjects were given two questionnaires. The first was a generic one about the subjects' purpose for using the internet and the length of

time they spent on it. Second, in order to determine the degree of Internet addiction, the Young's Internet Addiction Test (YIAT-20) was used. The first reliable and valid test for measuring online addiction is the online Addiction Test. Kimberley Young (1998) created this questionnaire consisting of twenty items. It rates cases of mild, moderate, and severe Internet addiction. Likert scale points range from 1 to 5 for each response. As a result, 1 represents infrequently, 2 represents occasionally, 3 represents frequently, 4 represents often, and 5 represents consistently.

The total of all the question scores is the final score. An increased level of addiction is indicated by a higher score. A total score of 20–49 indicates a mild addiction, 50–79 a moderate addiction, and 80–100 a severe addiction.

Findings and Analysis Result

A total of 125 undergraduate university students provided information for the study questionnaire. The subjects were from the nursing streams. Students were split up into three categories: moderate (30.50%), severe (8.25%), and mild (61.25%) online purchase utilization. Nursing students most frequently used the internet to order food and snack products (50.06%), clothes items (30.43%), travel/tour items (11.26%), and accessories (08.25%). The majority of nursing students (69.21%) had their daily online purchase assessments completed in less than three hours, followed by those who completed their assessments in three to six hours and those who completed their assessments in eight to ten hours.

Table 1- Analysis on extent of online Purchase users in Internet (N=125)

Online Internet Used for Purchase	Number	Percentage
20-49 (Mild online purchaser)	77	61.25
50-79 (Moderate online purchaser)	38	30.50
80-100 (Severe online purchaser)	10	08.25

According to Table 1 above, 61.25 percent of nursing students received a score of 20–49 (mild online purchaser), 30.50 percent received a score of 50–79 (moderate online purchaser), and 08.25 percent received a score of 80–100 (severe online purchaser).

Table: 02 Analysis on frequency of online usage purpose of online purchase (N=125)

Purpose of Online used for online Purchase / Order online items	Number	Percentage
Food and Snacks	63	50.06
Accessories	10	08.25
Travel/Tours	14	11.26
Dress / Readymade	38	30.43

According to table 2 above, ordering food and snacks was found to be the most popular online use by nursing students (50.06%). Ordering dresses (30.43%), travel tickets and tours (11.26%), and accessories (08.25%) were the next most popular online purchases.

Table 3- Analysis on duration of online purchase /ordering.

Online search for purchase items	Number	Percentage
Less than 03 Hours	87	69.21
03 - 06 Hours	28	22.79
06 – 08 Hours	10	08.0

Table 3 above demonstrates that 69.21% of students evaluated their use of the Internet for online purchases less than three hours per day, 22.79% of students for purchases between three and six hours, and 08.0% of nursing students for purchases between six and eight hours per day.

Recommendations

- To gain further insight into online nursing purchases and their detrimental impact on cognitive functioning, longitudinal research is required.
- The study might be expanded to include more demographic factors like age, gender, and place of residence, as well as additional cognitive functions including learning,

memorization, comprehension levels, information analysis and interpretation, and so forth.

Discussion

Based on the study's findings, nursing students used the internet at a rate of 61.25% for mild online stock purchases or orders, 30.50% for moderate online stock purchases or orders, and 8.50% for severe online stock purchases or orders; this statistic is thought to be high based on other studies done in India and overseas. The prevalence of Internet addiction (representing mild, moderate, and severe addiction) was estimated in this study, which is consistent with the majority of studies that used Young's Internet addiction test to determine the prevalence of Internet addiction.

Conclusion

Nursing students are increasingly struggling with internet addiction, online gaming, and many of them use the internet primarily for social networking sites like (Zomato , Swiggy, Domino's Pizza, Amazon, Flipkart, Myntra, Nykaa , Ajo, Snapdeal, Meesho,Tatacliq, Facebook, WhatsApp).

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